

A New Leakage Correction for Axial Void Channels in the 2D/1D Method

Sooyoung Choi¹, Edward Larsen¹, Brendan Kochunas^{1,*}

¹University of Michigan, 2355 Bonisteel Blvd, Ann Arbor, MI, USA

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ABSTRACT

A new leakage correction method is proposed to improve the accuracy and stability of 2D/1D transport calculations, particularly for microreactor designs containing large void regions, such as empty guide tubes. The new method introduces a leakage correction cross section, which is numerically derived from a simple one-group 2D slab fixed-source problem and subsequently incorporated into the axial equation of the 2D/1D method. This approach ensures that the scalar flux in void regions more closely matches the results obtained from a full transport solution. Implementation in MPACT demonstrates significant improvements in k_{eff} and axial power distribution compared to the standard 2D/1D method. Furthermore, the new method enhances convergence stability, reducing the required number of iterations.

Keywords: 2D/1D method, void, leakage correction cross section, microreactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, we have been developing the high-fidelity reactor physics solver MPACT [1], extending its capabilities to support the modeling of heat-pipe microreactor designs [2, 3]. As a part of this effort, we are investigating the application of the 2D/1D method [4, 5] to solve the three-dimensional Boltzmann transport equation for microreactors, since we believe the 2D/1D method offers an effective compromise between accuracy and computational cost for whole-core analyses.

In our recent work [3], we implemented several techniques to address stability issues encountered by the 2D/1D method when applied to microreactor designs with large void regions, such as those found in guide tubes. While these approaches improve stability, we have observed that accuracy still degrades significantly in problems with axial void regions. This degradation is primarily due to the isotropic assumption made for the Transverse Leakage (TL) source, as is typically done in the standard 2D/1D method.

MPACT has several variations of the 2D/1D method that modify the angular dependency of the TL and the cross section when coupling the 2D and 1D problems [6, 7]. However, the 2D/1D method with an angle-dependent TL is generally less stable and still requires further improvements in stability. Additionally, these angle-dependent methods tend to require more computational resources compared to the standard isotropic 2D/1D method.

In Section 2, we briefly review the standard 2D/1D method and its angle-dependent variations. Section 3 then introduces a modified 2D/1D method that incorporates a leakage correction cross section to improve accuracy in axial void regions. In this approach, we retain the 2D/1D method based on the isotropic treatment of the TL, while the leakage correction cross section enables the scalar flux in void regions to more closely match the results from a full transport calculation. Section 4 demonstrates the improvements in accuracy and stability achieved by the new method through its application to 3D assembly problems, and Section 5 summarizes the key findings of this work.

*bkochuna@umich.edu

2. STANDARD 2D/1D METHOD

The 2D/1D method is the primary approach used in MPACT for three-dimensional whole-core transport calculations [5]. This method decomposes the 3D Boltzmann transport equation into 2D radial plane and 1D axial problems. Here we summarize the fundamental equations.

The governing equation for the 2D radial solver is formulated and typically solved using the 2D Method of Characteristics (MOC):

$$\left[\Omega_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Omega_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right] \psi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) + \Sigma_{tr,g}(\mathbf{r}) \psi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} [q_g(\mathbf{r}) - \bar{L}_{z,g}(\mathbf{r})] , \quad (1)$$

where g is the energy group index; \mathbf{r} is the position vector; $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is the direction vector; ψ_g is the angular flux; $\Sigma_{tr,g}$ is the transport cross section; q_g is the sum of fission and scattering sources; and $\bar{L}_{z,g}$ is the *isotropic* axial TL.

The governing equation for the 1D axial solver is formulated for a coarse mesh homogenized cell as follows:

$$\Omega_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) + \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}(\mathbf{r}) \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} [\bar{q}_g(\mathbf{r}) - \bar{L}_{xy,g}(\mathbf{r})] , \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{L}_{xy,g}^{k,j}$ is the *isotropic* radial TL; the overbar, $(\bar{\cdot})$, denotes the homogenized quantity for a coarse mesh cell (typically a unit pin cell). The specific homogenization procedure is omitted here for brevity.

The isotropic axial and radial TLs are defined as follow:

$$\bar{L}_{z,g}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_{4\pi} \Omega_z \psi_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) d\Omega ; \quad \bar{L}_{xy,g}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{4\pi} \Omega_x \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) d\Omega + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_{4\pi} \Omega_y \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) d\Omega . \quad (3)$$

The radial and axial equations are solved iteratively by exchanging sources and TLs through source iteration, which is typically accelerated using Coarse Mesh Finite Difference (CMFD).

The accuracy of the 2D/1D method with isotropic TL can be degraded when the TL is highly anisotropic and the affected region is of particular importance in the problem [6]. In practical Light Water Reactors (LWR) applications, however, the isotropic TL generally provides sufficient accuracy, making the use of angle-dependent TL methods rarely necessary. Additionally, angle-dependent TL methods are typically less computationally efficient and can potentially impair the stability of 2D/1D iterations [7]. As a result, angle-dependent TL methods have, to date, been primarily of research interest rather than practical application. However, in the microreactor design, there exists a large guide tube – exceeding the size of a unit pin cell – that is filled with inert gas. For this configuration, the 2D/1D method with isotropic TL yields poor accuracy; this is demonstrated in Section 4 presented later in the manuscript.

We initially attempted to improve the stability of the angle-dependent TL 2D/1D method. However, we observed that even when the method is stabilized, the iteration process remains very slow in the presence of large void regions. We presume that this is because, in void regions, the angle-dependent TL is the primary mechanism through which the radial and axial equations *communicate*. However, the CMFD method cannot accelerate the angle-dependent TL or the angular flux for each angle. As a result, the approach with angle-dependent TL is likely even more computationally inefficient for problems with large void regions, indicating that a different acceleration or 2D/1D coupling method may be necessary. Therefore, rather than relying on the angle-dependent TL method, we propose an alternative approach, described in the following section.

3. MODIFIED 2D/1D METHOD

The isotropic TL assumption in the void channel causes Equation (2) to overestimate both the axial net current and axial TL. As a result, neutrons in the void region are transported away too rapidly in the

axial direction, leading to an overestimation of axial leakage, $\bar{L}_{z,g}$. In the 2D equation, the overestimated axial leakage leads to a significant decrease in the neutron population within the void region. To remedy this situation, the modified 2D/1D method introduces a leakage correction cross section to the axial equation as follows:

$$\Omega_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) + [\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,g}(\mathbf{r}) + \bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}(\mathbf{r})] \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi} [\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}(\mathbf{r}) \bar{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) + \bar{q}_g(\mathbf{r}) - \bar{L}_{xy,g}(\mathbf{r})] , \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$ is the leakage correction cross section; $\bar{\phi}$ is the scalar flux defined as $\bar{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{4\pi} \bar{\psi}_g(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) d\Omega$.

In the modified 2D/1D method, the radial equation remains unchanged, as indicated in Equation (1). However, $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$ is introduced to both the collision and source terms of the axial equation. The inclusion of $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$ increases neutron collisions within the void channel, thereby providing greater opportunity for neutrons to leak radially during iterative coupling with the radial solver. Since $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$, the self-scattering cross section, is added to both sides of the equation, overall neutron balance is maintained.

With a suitable choice of $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$, the axial 1D equation is expected to provide a more accurate estimation of axial leakage compared to the standard formulation. To determine $\bar{\Sigma}_{L,g}$, we use an optimization procedure to identify the value that best preserves the full transport scalar flux profile.

We devise a one-group 2D slab void channel problem on the x - y plane, with height h_y and width h_x , but infinitely extruded in the z -direction, as depicted in Figure 1. In this 2D problem, the x and y directions represent the radial and axial directions, respectively, of the standard 2D/1D equations. Isotropic angular flux is imposed as a boundary condition at the surface as follows:

$$\psi_0(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \cos(|B|(y - h_y/2)) , & x = 0 \text{ or } x = h_x , \\ \cos(|B|(-h_y/2)) , & y = 0 \text{ or } y = h_y , \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. 2D slab void channel

where B^2 is the source buckling, which is one of the specifications of the 2D problem.

This cosine-shaped isotropic incoming angular flux is intended to emulate the neutron flux entering the large void guide tube in the actual problem. We are currently using $B = \pi/(1.1h_y)$ to emulate the neutron source coming from top and bottom of the void channel and to simplify the problem setup, integrating the h_y with the buckling together. While the choice of buckling has some sensitivity in the results, its overall impact remains minor; further investigation will be addressed in future work.

For the problem setup, the 2D transport solution of Equation (6) is used as a reference for the optimization process. The 2D MOC or Collision Probability Method (CPM) can be used for the calculation.

$$\left[\Omega_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Omega_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right] \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) + \Sigma_t \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) = 0 , \quad (6)$$

where Σ_t is the total cross section of the void region, which is assumed to be spatially constant and 10^{-5}cm^{-1} . We further assume that the void region has no scattering cross section.

To emulate the 2D/1D method, we solve the same problem using a set of 1D/1D equations, as shown in Equation (7). These equations can be solved using a 1D S_N method, incorporating both spatial and angular discretization, along with source iteration.

$$\Omega_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) + \Sigma_t \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) = \frac{-L_y(\mathbf{r})}{4\pi} , \quad (7a)$$

$$\Omega_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) + [\Sigma_t + \Sigma_L] \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi} [\Sigma_L \phi(\mathbf{r}) - L_x(\mathbf{r})] . \quad (7b)$$

We seek to determine Σ_L such that the radially integrated axial scalar fluxes from the 2D equation, $\phi_{2D}(y)$, and the 1D/1D equation, $\phi_{1D1D}(y)$, are the same. The optimization procedure to determine Σ_L , outlined in Algorithm 1, first solves the 2D equations, and then solve the 1D/1D equations while varying Σ_L to minimize the error between the axial flux profiles computed by the 2D and 1D/1D methods. Approximately 10–20 optimization iterations are required to achieve convergence.

Algorithm 1 Optimization of Σ_L

- 1: **Initialize:** Set up problem using inputs h_x, h_y
- 2: Solve the 2D problem (Equation (6)) to obtain $\phi_{2D}(y)$
- 3: **for** each optimization iteration **do**
- 4: Estimate Σ_L via Golden-section search
- 5: **for** each 1D/1D source iteration **do**
- 6: Solve the axial 1D problem (Equation (7b))
- 7: Solve the radial 1D problem (Equation (7a))
- 8: Break if $\phi_{1D1D}(y)$ converged
- 9: **end for**
- 10: Compare $\phi_{2D}(y)$ and $\phi_{1D1D}(y)$
- 11: Break if optimal Σ_L found
- 12: **end for**

Figure 2. Leakage correction cross sections

Figure 2 displays Σ_L over a wide range of void channel widths and heights potentially encountered in practical situations, specifically for $h_x \in [0.1, 5.0]$ cm and $h_y \in [10, 400]$ cm. For practical applications, this data can be organized in an interpolation table or represented using a fitted function. In MPACT, we implement a rational equation fitted to the data, as shown in Figure 2.

For the application of Σ_L to the actual 3D cylindrical void channel, we employ mean chord length equivalence instead of directly solving the equations in r - z coordinates. This approach allows Σ_L to be applied more universally, regardless of the specific geometry.

The final aspect to consider for implementation is the consideration of the total cross section in void regions. Since Σ_L is designed to correct leakage in regions where the total cross section is nearly zero (e.g., 10^{-5} cm $^{-1}$), it is important to reduce Σ_L when the void region presents a higher cross section due to material properties. Additionally, the 2D/1D method applies coarse mesh homogenization to solve the axial 1D equation, rather than using the fine mesh region directly. As a result, the homogenized total cross section for a coarse mesh cell may be greater than that of the actual void region. To simultaneously address these two cases, we first calculate the homogenized leakage correction cross section as follows:

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{L,I,g} = \frac{\sum_{i \in I_{\text{void}}} \max(0, \Sigma_L(h_x, h_y) - \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g}) \phi_{i,g} V_i}{\sum_{i \in I} \phi_{i,g} V_i}; \quad \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g} = \frac{\sum_{i \in I} \Sigma_{tr,i,g} \phi_{i,g} V_i}{\sum_{i \in I} \phi_{i,g} V_i}, \quad (8)$$

where i is the fine mesh (or MOC flat source region) index; I is the coarse mesh index; I_{void} denotes the void region within coarse mesh I ; $\phi_{i,g}$ is the scalar flux in fine mesh i and group g ; V_i is the volume of region i ; $\Sigma_L(h_x, h_y)$ denotes the function-fitted or tabulated leakage correction cross section; $\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g}$ is the uncorrected homogenized transport cross section.

Equation (8) calculates the homogenized leakage cross section using the flux-volume weighted average of the difference between $\Sigma_L(h_x, h_y)$ and $\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g}$. In this context, $\Sigma_L(h_x, h_y)$ represents the minimum total cross section required to achieve a full-transport-like scalar flux with the 2D/1D method. Therefore, if the transport cross section exceeds this threshold, no additional leakage cross section is needed. Once the homogenized leakage correction cross section is calculated, the subsequent axial nodal calculation is performed with the updated transport and self-scattering cross sections as follows:

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g} \leftarrow \bar{\Sigma}_{tr,I,g} + \bar{\Sigma}_{L,I,g}; \quad \bar{\Sigma}_{s,I,g \rightarrow g} \leftarrow \bar{\Sigma}_{s,I,g \rightarrow g} + \bar{\Sigma}_{L,I,g}. \quad (9)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Figure 3. EMD microreactor assembly

The modified 2D/1D method is tested on a microreactor assembly design featuring a large guide tube and heat pipes that contain void regions. The assembly design is based on the eVinciTM Motivated Design (EMD) [8], with a few minor modifications. Problem specifications for the EMD assembly case are briefly described in Figure 3. Graphite serves as the moderator in the active fuel region, while BeO is used in both the upper and lower reflector regions. The upper and lower plates are composed of SS304 stainless steel. A shutdown rod guide tube is located at the assembly center. While the guide tube is typically extend to the lower reflector and plate regions, in this study, we simplify the model to facilitate verification of the method. Heat pipes are placed within the active fuel region and extend up to the upper reflector and plate. The fuel kernel consists of UCO enriched to 19.75%, encapsulated in TRISO-structural ISotropic (TRISO) particles with five layers. The packing fraction of the fuel compact is 40%.

Additional problem cases based on the original 3D assembly configuration were investigated. These cases include:

1. $r = 1.7$ cm: The original problem specification; the central coarse mesh cell is entirely within the void region.
2. $r = 1.4$ cm: A smaller tube radius than the original case; the void region is completely contained within the central hexagonal coarse mesh cell.
3. $r = 2.0$ cm: A larger tube radius than the original case; the void region extends beyond the central cell.
4. Graphite-filled: The guide tube dimension is the same as in the $r = 1.7$ cm case, but the void region is filled with graphite instead of being empty.

For this test, we implemented the modified 2D/1D method in MPACT. The radial solver employs the 2D MOC with the Sanchez-Pomraning (S-P) method [9] for TRISO double-heterogeneity treatment, while the axial solver uses the 1D hybrid P_3 nodal method. Although the modified 2D/1D method was developed based on the transport equation in the axial direction, we confirmed that the P_3 nodal method yields results very similar to the 1D S_N method when using the equivalent scattering cross section. The 252-group cross-section library was used for these simulations. Reference solutions were generated using OpenMC [10]. Test cases were evaluated using both the standard 2D/1D and the modified 2D/1D methods for comparison. When using the 2D/1D method with Σ_L , the leakage correction cross section is applied to all void regions, including the central guide tube and heat pipes.

Table I. EMD 3D assembly type 2 simulation results

Problem Cases	Method	k_{eff}	k_{eff} diff. (pcm)	1D RMS diff. (%) ^a	1D Max diff. (%) ^b	2D RMS diff. (%) ^c	3D RMS diff. (%) ^d
Tube $r=1.4$ cm	OpenMC	1.09897	± 13	± 0.19	± 0.23	± 0.19	± 0.19
	2D/1D	1.09892	-5	0.54	1.30	0.04	0.58
	2D/1D with Σ_L	1.09940	43	0.18	0.49	0.04	0.25
Tube $r=1.7$ cm	OpenMC	1.07886	± 13	± 0.19	± 0.23	± 0.19	± 0.19
	2D/1D	1.06398	-1488	16.76	43.09	0.04	16.75
	2D/1D with Σ_L	1.07927	40	0.26	0.62	0.04	0.30
Tube $r=2.0$ cm	OpenMC	1.05884	± 13	± 0.19	± 0.23	± 0.19	± 0.19
	2D/1D	1.04454	-1430	16.64	42.97	0.04	16.64
	2D/1D with Σ_L	1.05953	68	0.13	0.34	0.03	0.22
Graphite filled tube	OpenMC	1.08353	± 13	± 0.19	± 0.22	± 0.19	± 0.19
	2D/1D	1.08467	114	0.13	0.36	0.02	0.21
	2D/1D with Σ_L	1.08468	114	0.14	0.38	0.02	0.22

^a RMS error for the radially integrated axial pin fission rate distribution, calculated using absolute differences.

^b Maximum error for the radially integrated axial pin fission rate distribution.

^c RMS error for the axially integrated radial pin fission rate distribution.

^d RMS error for the 3D pin fission rate distribution.

* Integrated standard deviations are estimated from pin-wise values.

Figure 4. Axial fission rate distribution results

The results are presented in Table I, and the radially integrated axial power distribution is also presented in Figure 4. First, for the original design with $r=1.7$ cm, the 2D/1D method significantly underestimates k_{eff} , resulting in a bias larger than 1,000 pcm. The axial power profile is also very inaccurate, appearing nearly flat in the axial direction. Most of the error occurs at the center coarse mesh, which is entirely void region. On the other hand, the 2D/1D method with Σ_L noticeably improves both k_{eff} and pin power distribution results. The k_{eff} difference is reduced to 40 pcm, and the axial power RMS difference is 0.26%. Similar trends are observed for the larger tube case with $r=2.0$ cm.

On the other hand, for $r=1.4$ cm, the standard 2D/1D method appears to yield reasonable results. The k_{eff} difference is -5 pcm and the axial RMS power difference is 0.54%. For this problem, the coarse mesh at the center is homogenized with both void and cladding, increasing the total cross section. Although the accuracy is acceptable, it can be further improved by using the modified 2D/1D method. With the modified 2D/1D, the k_{eff} difference is 43 pcm and the axial power RMS difference decreases to 0.18%. These results indicate that the leakage correction cross section is also important for coarse mesh regions that are not entirely void.

The last case is a graphite-filled guide tube, so that only the impact on the heat-pipe region can be observed. For this scenario, the accuracy difference between the standard 2D/1D and modified 2D/1D methods is not noticeable; both show order of 0.14% RMS difference in the axial power distribution. A coarse mesh cell containing the heat pipe includes cladding and moderator materials, resulting in a sufficiently large homogenized cross section, so the impact of using the leakage correction cross section is minimal.

Another key advantage of the modified 2D/1D method is its enhanced computational efficiency, resulting from improved convergence stability compared to the standard approach. The standard 2D/1D method often depends on underrelaxation to maintain stability; however, this practice can reduce computational efficiency, as it potentially increases the number of outer iterations needed for convergence [3]. Specifically, the underrelaxation technique requires that regions with optically thin materials or small cross sections adopt a smaller relaxation factor—often close to zero—to guarantee stability. The modified 2D/1D method improves convergence stability by increasing the total cross section within coarse mesh cells. The method permits the use of a larger relaxation factor and results in a reduced spectral radius.

Figure 5. Convergence behavior (Case with $r=1.7$)

Figure 5 depicts the convergence behavior with and without the application of the leakage correction cross section. Using the modified 2D/1D method, only 10 outer iterations were required to achieve convergence, compared to 24 iterations for the standard 2D/1D method. Both simulations utilized the space-dependent relaxation method [3].

Although the demonstrations presented here show good agreement across all cases, we have observed that further investigation is necessary, particularly in situations where the guide tube extends outside the active core region. Additionally, we noticed that accounting for the spatial dependency of the leakage correction cross section may further enhance the accuracy of our results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A modified 2D/1D method introducing a leakage correction cross section, Σ_L , has been developed to address the accuracy limitations of the standard 2D/1D approach in problems with large void regions, such as heat-pipe microreactors or gas reactors. The leakage correction cross section is derived numerically from a simplified one-group fixed-source 2D slab problem and incorporated into the axial equation of the 2D/1D method to closely match the full transport scalar flux. Numerical tests for the 3D microreactor assembly problems demonstrate that this approach significantly improves the estimation of both k_{eff} and the power distribution. This yields approximately 100 pcm k_{eff} difference and 0.2% RMS axial power distribution difference. The leakage correction also enhances run-time performance by improving the stability of the 2D/1D method, resulting in roughly half the number of iterations required to reach convergence. Overall, the leakage correction cross section in the modified 2D/1D method is straightforward to implement and obtain, improves the convergence of 2D/1D calculations, and greatly enhances their accuracy for practical problems. This approach has strong potential to further extend the applicability of the 2D/1D method.

Future work will focus on deriving analytic expressions for the cross section correction, rather than continuing to rely on an empirical fit of numerical data from a simplified problem.

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